

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AS A CATALYST FOR INDUSTRIAL LOCALIZATION AND COOPERATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on examining how digitalization influences the localization of production processes and the growth of industrial cooperation in Uzbekistan. In the context of accelerated digital transformation of the global economy, digitalization is becoming a key tool for increasing technological independence, production efficiency, and integration into global value chains. Based on statistical data from international organizations (World Bank, UN Comtrade, WIPO, ADB), it is shown that between 2015 and 2023, Uzbekistan experienced a growth in the share of medium- and high-tech industries, an increase in high-tech product exports, and an expansion of digital infrastructure. The implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan—2030" state strategy contributes to the formation of national digital ecosystems, the development of technology parks, and the introduction of ERP systems, IoT, and AI solutions in industry. It is concluded that digitalization is one of the factors in strengthening Uzbekistan's technological sovereignty and transitioning to an innovative economic growth model based on the synergy of digital technologies, localization, and industrial cooperation..

Introduction. The digitalization of the global economy is becoming a key factor in the transformation of production systems, international supply chains, and national industrial strategies. Modern technologies—from artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things (IoT) to automation and big data analysis—are shaping new forms of industrial cooperation and changing the structure of national industry. For Central Asian countries, particularly Uzbekistan, digitalization serves as a tool to accelerate industrial development, increase efficiency of the localization, expand industrial cooperation, and integrate into global value chains. Digitalization reduces transaction costs, increases supply chain transparency, and stimulates the adoption of new creative solutions.

The digitalization of industry in emerging economies, including Uzbekistan, is becoming a key factor in strengthening technological independence and

competitiveness¹. The implementation of artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, and cloud solutions optimizes production processes, reduces costs, and increases the resilience of supply chains². The study indicated that digitalization contributes to labor productivity growth and stimulates the creation of new forms of industrial cooperation³.

The State Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" is aimed, among other things, at integrating digital technologies into industry and developing information and communication technologies and infrastructure through comprehensive support for attracting foreign investment and local IT developers⁴. This will increase the localization level of the economy and reduce dependence on external suppliers. Additionally, digital ecosystems form a platform for effective cooperation between all market participants, especially in "B2B," "B2G," and "B2C" formats. Additionally, digitalization contributes to strengthening the skills of personnel and creating new competencies. Thus, digitalization serves not only as a tool for economic efficiency but also as the foundation for technological sovereignty and the expansion of production localization.

Digitalization lays the conceptual foundations for both digitalization and industrial cooperation. The digitalization of industry is considered a key direction of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0)⁵. According to the concept of digital industrialization (UNIDO, 2020)⁶, digital technologies are shaping a new paradigm for production organization, where networked interaction is created between enterprises, suppliers, and consumers. The result contributes to the formation of flexible production systems and accelerates the processes of localization and industrial cooperation.

From the perspective of neoinstitutional theory, digitalization reduces transaction costs (W. North, 1990)⁷ and contributes to the formation of more transparent and efficient mechanisms of interaction between economic agents. In the context of global value chain theory (Gereffi, 2018)⁸, digital transformation acts as a factor that

¹ Muratbekova, A. (2024). *Digitalization in Central Asia: Progress and Potential*. In *Digital Diplomacy in the OSCE Region: From Theory to Practice*. Springer. (https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-50966-7_4)

² Nechaev, A. S., Morozevich, O. A., Kuznetsova, O. N. (2021). *The Impact of Digitalization in the Economy on the Infrastructure of North and Central Asia*. In *Digital and Information Technologies in Economics and Management*. Springer. (https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-97730-6_17)

³ Shahzad, U., & Muhammad, S. (2025). *Digital pathways to sustainability: The role of Europe-Central Asia region's digitalization, trade, and geography maximizing sustainable development in China*. *Journal of Environmental Management*, Elsevier. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301479725033171>)

⁴ PF-6079 dated 05.10.2020. On approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation (<https://lex.uz/docs/5030957#>)

⁵ Шерр, А.-В. Индустрия 4.0. От прорывной бизнес-модели к автоматизации бизнес-процессов / Август-Вильгельм Шерр ; пер. с нем. — М.: Альпина Паблишер, 2018. — 264 с.

⁶ United Nations Industrial Development Organization, 2019. *Industrial Development Report 2020. Industrializing in the digital age*. Vienna. (<https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/unido-publications/2023-03/UNIDO-IDR2020-main-report-en.pdf>)

⁷ North, D. C. *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. — Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990.

⁸ Gereffi, G. *Global Value Chains and International Development: Policy Implications in a Digital World*. *Journal of International Business Policy*, 2018, Vol. 1(3–4), pp. 279–307.

strengthens the integration of developing countries into the international industrial division of labor.

Results and Discussion.

Between 2015 and 2024, Uzbekistan's industrial sector demonstrated a significant shift toward technological modernization. According to the Agency of Statistics⁹, the country's GDP growth rate reached **6.5% in 2024**, marking one of the highest figures of the past five years. The share of industry in GDP increased from **25.3% to 26.4%**, while **manufacturing output grew by 7.7%**. The **information and communication technology (ICT)** sector expanded by **24.7% in 2024**, reflecting the accelerated development of digital infrastructure and services. At the same time, **machinery and equipment still account for 34.6% of total imports**, emphasizing the need for further localization of high-tech components. The share of **small businesses** in industrial production rose from **27% to 32.4%**, indicating the successful integration of SMEs into industrial cooperation networks. This growth was driven by the development of digital manufacturing systems, supply chain localization, and the implementation of solutions based on ERP platforms, the Internet of Things (IoT), and big data analytics, which allowed for the optimization of production and logistics processes. These changes were achieved through the widespread implementation of digital solutions in the financial and banking system, manufacturing enterprises, the creation of modern production facilities, and the strengthening of industrial cooperation between domestic and foreign companies.

Expert research indicates that the use of digital platforms and AI-based solutions in Central Asian industries has accelerated information exchange, reduced transaction costs, and increased production flexibility. Simultaneously, digitalization has increased supply chain transparency, strengthening the interconnectedness between sectors and regions¹⁰.

According to the UN Comtrade Database¹¹, Uzbekistan's high-tech goods exports increased from approximately US \$1 billion in 2015 to US \$2 billion in 2023, with the main export items being electronic components, pharmaceutical products, and machinery equipment. Similar trends were noted in the WIPO Statistics Database¹²: the global volume of high-tech goods exports increased by 9.1% in 2023 compared to 2022, with the largest segments being electronics and IT components, integrated circuits, and pharmaceuticals.

The 2024 Trade Data Monitor report indicates that similar trends are observed in Central Asia, where the share of high value-added exports is growing, particularly in the engineering and logistics sectors. Overall, the localization and digitalization of

⁹ **Agency of Statistics** under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Database. (2024). Available at: <https://stat.uz/ru/press-tsentr/novosti-goskomstata/59509-werwerw>

¹⁰ **Bokayev, B., Amirova, A., & Galy, A. (2024).** *Innovative Approaches to Public Services Delivery through the Prism of the Industry 5.0 Paradigm. The Innovation Journal*, 29(3). https://innovation.cc/wp-content/uploads/2024_29_3_2_bokayev_innovative-approaches-public-services-delivery-through-prism-of-the-industry-50-paradigm-2.pdf

¹¹ **UN Comtrade** <https://comtradeplus.un.org/>

¹² **WIPO IP Statistics Data Center** <https://www3.wipo.int/ipstats/key-search/indicator>

production in Uzbekistan have contributed to reducing import dependence, increasing employment, and diversifying the industrial structure.

Digitalization acts as a powerful catalyst for the processes of production localization and industrial cooperation in Uzbekistan. It strengthens the link between innovation, industry, and employment, creating the conditions for long-term sustainable growth of the national economy. The development of national digital services such as "Virtual Data Center," "Co-location," and "BMS Server," and the "The Register of E-commerce Entities E-tijorat.uz," as well as digital platforms like the "Single Portal of Interactive Public Services," the "Public Procurement Portal," and the "Electronic Cooperation Portal," contributes to the formation of integrated supply chains and simplifies access to information, public.

Additionally, the development of communication infrastructure and data centers enhances the competitiveness of regional manufacturing hubs. According to the Asian Development Bank¹³, Uzbekistan's investment in digital infrastructure exceeded US \$4 billion between 2019 and 2023, and the proportion of enterprises using automation systems and cloud services increased from 22% to 47%. These processes are directly linked to the growth of employment in the ICT sector, where the number of specialists has increased by over 60% in the past five years, indicating the formation of a new model of digital employment.

Thus, digitalization is becoming a strategic tool for strengthening Uzbekistan's technological sovereignty and industrial independence. It facilitates the transition from a resource-oriented model to a knowledge economy, stimulates innovation, and forms sustainable production networks. In the long term, the digital transformation of the industrial sector can become a key driver for increasing the competitiveness of Central Asian countries and accelerating regional economic integration processes, as well as expanding participation in global technological and production chains.

For Uzbekistan, digitalization is becoming a key driver of growth in technological independence. In this context, localization and industrial cooperation allow for a reduction in import dependence, an increase in employment in the IT sector, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, electronics, and logistics, and an enhancement of export diversification. The comprehensive use of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence and cloud computing, will strengthen production clusters and accelerate the country's integration into global innovation chains. Thus, digital modernization serves as a key mechanism for enhancing Uzbekistan's technological sovereignty and ensures the transition to an innovative economic growth model based on the synergy of localization, digital technologies, and industrial cooperation.

The main mechanisms of digitalization's influence on localization and industrial cooperation processes are manifested in three key areas:

1. Reducing transaction costs. In the study "An Empirical Investigation into the Effects of the Digital Economy on Regional Integration in China" published in

¹³ Asian Development Bank — Uzbekistan country page (с открытыми отчётами)
<https://www.adb.org/countries/uzbekistan/main>

Sustainability (MDPI, 2024)¹⁴, it was found that digital industrialization increases the level of regional integration and industrial cooperation: the regression coefficients were 0.24 for digital industrialization and 0.128 for industrial digitalization ($p < 0.01$). Similar effects can be achieved in Central Asian countries through digital logistics platforms and wider utilization of digital platform capabilities.

2. Increasing production efficiency. The integration of ERP systems, modern Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics allows for the optimization of resource management, improvement of product quality, and increased flexibility of production systems.

3. Improving the efficiency of industrial cooperation. Digital platforms and manufacturing management systems enable horizontal and vertical cooperation. The study "Impact of Digitalization and Supply Chain Integration on Sustainable Supply Chain Performance (Morocco, 2022)" showed that digitalization increases supply chain integration, leading to improved overall productivity.

At the same time, in the context of the transition to a digital economy, Central Asian countries face a complex stage of transformation – from partial informatization of individual production processes to comprehensive digitalization at the level of the entire production system. Digital transformation serves not only as a tool for modernization but also as a systemic factor in increasing the efficiency and sustainability of the industrial sector.

The importance of an in-depth understanding of the mechanisms of digital transformation and innovative enterprise development is increasing. The use of digital ecosystems, electronic platforms, and big data analytics tools opens up opportunities to improve interactions with suppliers, consumers, and collaborative partners. In this context, an important direction becomes the formation of policies that ensure an effective combination of digital and traditional enterprise resources, the development of human capital, and the stimulation of staff creative activity. These factors slow down the pace of transformation and require targeted government support measures. In this regard, government policy should be aimed at improving the intellectual property protection system, supporting innovative collaborations, and reducing barriers to corporate protectionism, which will create a favorable institutional environment for deepening industrial cooperation and increasing its technological effectiveness.

Conclusions and Recommendations (Policy Brief).

Digitalization is becoming a strategic driver for enhancing Uzbekistan's technological sovereignty and industrial independence. Analysis indicates that the integration of digital solutions into industry contributes to the growth of high-tech sectors, the reduction of transaction costs, and the improvement of localization processes. The implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan—2030" strategy has already created the institutional and infrastructural prerequisites for the formation of a digital industrial ecosystem.

¹⁴ Ru, L., Wang, P., & Lu, Y. (2024). An Empirical Investigation into the Effects of the Digital Economy on Regional Integration: Evidence from Urban Agglomeration in China. *Sustainability*, 16(17), 7760. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16177760>

To fully utilize the potential of digital technologies, accelerate the transition to an innovative growth model, and create the conditions for the formation of adaptive and innovation-oriented industrial development models, it is recommended:

Create specialized "smart zones" and technology parks in key sectors (industrial machinery, engineering, electronics, and pharmaceuticals) to integrate AI, IoT, and digital twins.

Implement a national Digital Maturity Index for businesses based on OECD and World Bank standards.

Develop human capital through educational programs in digital manufacturing, industrial analytics, and innovation management.

Create a state platform for industrial statistics and a digital map of supply chains, ensuring transparency and coordination of cooperative links.

Comprehensive digitalization of industry will allow Uzbekistan to strengthen its position in global production networks and ensure sustainable long-term economic growth.

Conclusion

The study shows that digitalization in Uzbekistan has moved from the stage of declarations to systemic industrial transformation. The State Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" lays the institutional and technological foundations for creating a national digital economy, increasing productivity, reducing transaction costs, and enhancing the transparency of supply chains.

Digitalization is becoming a key tool for strengthening technological sovereignty and transitioning Uzbekistan from a resource-oriented to an innovative model of economic growth. In the long term, the digital transformation of the industrial sector will contribute to deepening cooperation between enterprises, expanding domestic production, and increasing export potential. Targeted government policies are necessary to fully realize the digital potential by developing human capital, fostering innovative collaborations, and enhancing the institutional environment. Digitalization is not only a way to modernization, but it is also a way for Uzbekistan to join global and regional technological value chains and for the country's industries to grow in a sustainable way.

References:

- 1.Muratbekova, A. (2024). Digitalization in Central Asia: Progress and Potential. In Digital Diplomacy in the OSCE Region: From Theory to Practice. Springer. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-50966-7_4
- 2.Nechaev, A. S., Morozevich, O. A., & Kuznetsova, O. N. (2021). The Impact of Digitalization in the Economy on the Infrastructure of North and Central Asia. In Digital and Information Technologies in Economics and Management. Springer. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-97730-6_17
- 3.Shahzad, U., & Muhammad, S. (2025). Digital pathways to sustainability: The role of Europe–Central Asia region's digitalization, trade, and geography maximizing sustainable

- development in China. *Journal of Environmental Management* (Elsevier). Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301479725033171>
4. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2020). Decree No. PF-6079 “On Approval and Effective Implementation of the ‘Digital Uzbekistan – 2030’ Strategy” (in Uzbek). Available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/5030957>
5. Scheer, A.-W. (2018). *Industry 4.0: From Disruptive Business Model to Automation of Business Processes*. Moscow: Alpina Publisher.
6. United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO). (2019). *Industrial Development Report 2020: Industrializing in the Digital Age*. Vienna. Available at: <https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/unido-publications/2023-03/UNIDO-IDR2020-main-report-en.pdf>
7. North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
8. Gereffi, G. (2018). Global Value Chains and International Development: Policy Implications in a Digital World. *Journal of International Business Policy*, 1(3–4), 279–307.
9. World Bank. (2024). High-technology Exports (% of Manufactured Exports). Available at: <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>
10. Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Database. (2024). Available at: <https://stat.uz/ru/press-tsentr/novosti-goskomstata/59509-werwerw>
11. Bokayev, B., Amirova, A., & Galy, A. (2024). Innovative Approaches to Public Services Delivery through the Prism of the Industry 5.0 Paradigm. *The Innovation Journal*, 29(3). Available at: https://innovation.cc/wp-content/uploads/2024_29_3_2_bokayev_innovative-approaches-public-services-delivery-through-prism-of-the-industry-50-paradigm-2.pdf
12. United Nations Comtrade Database. (2024). *International Trade Statistics*. Available at: <https://comtradeplus.un.org/>
13. World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). (2024). IP Statistics Data Center. Available at: <https://www3.wipo.int/ipstats/key-search/indicator>
14. Rakhmatov, F. Q. (2023). The Role of Digital Technologies in Enhancing the Efficiency of Industrial Cooperation. *Proceedings of the International Scientific-Practical Conference “Digital Transformation in Business and Economy”*, Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, pp. 366–370. (in Uzbek). Available at: <https://rgsbm.uz/uploads/docs/7e84433e99fd1e87c4487c18b3b04c7c.pdf>
15. Asian Development Bank (ADB). (2024). Uzbekistan Country Page. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/countries/uzbekistan/main>
16. Ru, L., Wang, P., & Lu, Y. (2024). An Empirical Investigation into the Effects of the Digital Economy on Regional Integration: Evidence from Urban Agglomeration in China. *Sustainability*, 16(17), 7760. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16177760>
17. Rakhmatov, F. K., & Sadikova, D. R. (2025). Methodology for Assessing the Efficiency of Production Localization and Industrial Cooperation. *Economy of Central Asia*, 9(1), 29–52. DOI: 10.18334/asia.9.1.122876